

TRAINING FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDENTS TO BE MINDCHANGERS: A LOCAL PERSPECTIVE ON A GLOBAL ISSUE

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Abstract

This study is based on the empirical research carried out in the project *A Comparative and Transferable Approach to Education for Democratic Citizenship (ACTA)*, funded under the EEA and Norway Grants (2014-2021) and focused on developing students' transversal competences that lead to active citizenship during their academic activity. Starting from the premise that university curricula should integrate transversal skills and competences in order to improve the teaching-learning outcomes, and in direct relation to the targeted priorities bringing EU development policy and EU answers to global challenges, we emphasise once more the need to change first the teachers-to-be so that they would become mindchangers themselves in their future activities. Being actively involved in educating and shaping the society they live in, teachers should be equipped with appropriate skills and competences to better adapt to the changing way in which people interact with each other and perceive information and knowledge. One such skill that has become more important than ever before in the current context of digitalised education is the ability to think critically. This skill does not only help create habits of mind and behaviour, but also makes the learners, placed in the centre of the whole educational process, actively responsible for their own learning. Although it is generally considered that critical thinking skills, alongside other important transversal competences, are implicitly developed in the teaching activity, we consider it necessary to evaluate the level at which this skill is acquired. Therefore, the aim of our study is to determine the level of critical thinking of the students enrolled at the Faculty of Letters in Foreign Language (FL) programmes from the University of Craiova. In order to do that, we use the model and the assessment tool drawn up in the ACTA project to evaluate the critical thinking skills of a group of 50 students trained to become FL teachers when confronted with a problem-based situation. The evaluation is done by means of a questionnaire applied to a video and article excerpts about climate change (a global issue included in the EU 2030 Agenda) that tackles both students' critical thinking skills, and their capacity to actively respond to the problem in question. Overall, the results of the study show that although great efforts have been made to integrate the competence-based curriculum in the teaching/learning practice, there is still a stringent need to develop educational strategies in order to enhance critical thinking and to help our students act as mindchangers in their future career. Indirectly, our analysis could be further used to evaluate the implementation of competence-based curriculum and the quality of education at a local level, at a time when educators envisage the development of appropriate skills and competences that would lead to new ways of acting and thinking in a global context.

Keywords: critical thinking, assessment, education for sustainability, foreign languages.

1 INTRODUCTION

The world today has put emphasis on the recent technological advances which account for new behaviours, new actions and new learning opportunities. In dealing with the next generations of students, the so-called 'digital natives', the future teachers should be equipped with new skills and competences, since traditional teaching/learning practices are no longer valid in the era of digital education and multimodal teaching/learning. Never has this need been more obvious than in the new situation created by the COVID-19 pandemic nowadays.

There is a shift now from awareness to action, in the sense that the focus is on the power of people's belief in their own capacity to produce change, in their own role as world citizens. One key aspect to reach such goals is to foster critical thinking skills among the young generations, and endow them with the consciousness to take action, in addition to making them aware of the global and local realities around them. The justification is straightforward.

On the one hand, critical thinking is an important component of higher level competences - as both content and process - especially in teacher training [1]. Researchers have already acknowledged that this skill stands out as a fundamental cognitive resource [1, 2]. It basically refers "not only to questioning

all data, evidence and experts, but rather to developing criteria for evaluating them” [3 p1012]. It is a complex concept, with different meanings that can hardly be limited to one comprehensive definition. Additionally, critical thinking is much more than just thinking, it is reasoning, seeking out information, the ability “to develop independent opinions, to challenge one’s own personal or collective interest and overcome egocentric values” [3 p1012]. In recent decades, the idea of critical thinking has become ingrained in the educational system, although the concept of educating students to think critically is not particularly new, since, as early as the 1930s, Osborne (1934) stated that one of the major goals of education should be to develop ‘thought power’ in students [4 p402, apud. 5].

On the other hand, teachers are the best instruments to shape the young people, so it is an important task to prepare them for the challenging responsibilities of educating new generations in a continuously changing context. Teachers themselves have to be equipped with critical thinking skills in order to turn their future students into good critical thinkers. Therefore, critical thinking should be incorporated in teacher training programmes, in all fields and specialisations, since “it is a ‘sine qua non’ prerequisite for knowledge creation and is linked to human inventiveness and innovation” [1, 6].

However, European reports on education show that the level of implementing these desiderata differ from one country to another. Hence, according to the *Education and Training Monitor* for 2019, in Romania, initial teacher education offers very little preparation and practical training, particularly in modern teaching techniques or inclusive pedagogy [7 p4] and an immediate consequence is a low teaching quality [8]. Moreover, the teachers training assessment instruments (i.e. certification exams or tenure exams) address rather the theoretical knowledge “without being an authentic measure of on-the-job competence” [7 p4]. Even if, according to OECD [8], a solution to improve the quality of teaching would be to increase the number of existing teachers involved in continuing professional development, there are significant drawbacks related to these courses in the sense that teachers complained about their high costs, and course content and delivery not sufficiently adapted to their needs. Consequently, it is important to develop a high level of knowledge, skills and competences in the future teachers by the end of their academic training and the main challenge for the higher-education institutions’ (HEIs) academic staff involved in teacher training programmes is to creatively combine different approaches that go beyond the traditional boundaries of knowledge-based practices. Thus, although it is not an easy task to change mindsets and train future teachers to be mindchangers, the HEIs’ professors need to be flexible and permanently adapt materials, methodology and communication, so as to incorporate critical thinking skills in their courses and produce positive effects.

The Romanian higher education system has acknowledged the importance of critical thinking for the labour market and the shaping of active and responsible citizens. Both the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ARACIS) [9 p10] and the National Agency for Qualifications in Higher Education and Partnership with the Economic and Social Environment (ACPART) include critical thinking among the study disciplines at BA or MA level for Social, Political and Communication Sciences and consider it as an important ability to be developed in all the other study fields. Despite these favourable educational policies, it has been recently shown that the Romanian students do not have labour market relevant skills [7], including critical thinking.

Therefore, in our opinion, efforts should be done to remedy this situation and improve the students’ level of critical thinking. But how can we measure this level? How can we evaluate the efficacy of the teaching methods employed for its development? And more specifically, how can FL classes be connected to the development of critical thinking?

To answer these questions, acknowledging the idea put forth in UNESCO (2000) that developing instruments to measure critical thinking skills is a necessary step in assessing and improving the quality of education, we combine in this study the experience and the best practices gained from interdisciplinary projects carried out at the University of Craiova in partnership with European higher institutions and youth organisations [10-12]. More specifically, we use the assessment tool that we developed within the ACTA project [13] with the aim to firstly establish the level of critical thinking of students enrolled in FL programmes at the University of Craiova (Romania), and secondly identify their learning gaps that need further development.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

In terms of methodology, this study is a questionnaire-based qualitative analysis, involving collecting, interpreting and evaluating the students' written answers to open-ended questions, so that to obtain quantifiable data that is subsequently compared and ranked.

The evaluation was done by means of a problem-based test questionnaire referring to global warming, an environmental issue included in the EU 2030 Agenda. The test was applied to a video available online and two article excerpts on this topic and was aimed to evaluate both students' critical thinking skills, and their capacity to actively respond to the problem in question.

The problem-based test comprised 6 open-ended questions and was designed to take students approximately 90 minutes to complete. The recommendation was that each answer should not exceed 100 words. The questions were drawn up in English and the students were asked to write their answers in English as well. As regards their foreign language proficiency, the expected level was B2, based on the admission requirements for foreign language programmes at the University of Craiova. In the very limited cases when students did not fully understand the content of the questionnaire, because of their lower level of FL competence, the teacher acted as facilitator and helped them to fully grasp the meaning of the questions and to formulate their answers. All in all, there were no language barriers that prevented the participants from completing the tasks.

In short, the assessment took place as follows: the students were invited to watch the video, read the two excerpts, and provide mindful solutions to the problems raised. After a brief introduction on the structure of the questionnaire, the teacher encouraged them to use their previous knowledge and personal experience in answering the questions, as well as any online or off-line resources that might help them to support their arguments.

The test designed within the ACTA project was aimed at assessing critical thinking and active citizenship. More specifically, questions 1, 2 and 6 targeted critical thinking, whereas questions 3, 4 and 5, active citizenship [13]. The two competences were then associated with their own assessment model, whose two parts, interpretation structures and action structures, were organised in four levels: non-autonomous, weak, intermediate, and advanced. Each competence was characterised in terms of "indicators – which are general and applicable to categories of situations – and descriptors, which are specific to a precise situation" [12 p125]. The elaboration of the descriptors associated with the situation described in the problem-based test followed the RIZA model proposed in Trincherio [14] and successfully applied in Tilea, Morin and Duta [12]. The model comprises four elements: Resources/Risorse, Interpretation/Interpretazione, Action/aZione, Self-Regulation/Autoregolazione [14], which "characterise the possibility to act effectively in a situation and, hence, the 'depth' of the subject's competence" [12 p126]. In the model used, the reference is made to the interpretation structures, defined as "the explicit or implicit models guiding the subject's interpretation of the issue and the choice of the used strategies" and to the action structures, as elements that deal with "the concrete operational strategies used to reach the envisaged goals, in the presence of a given problem-based test". [12 p126]

To make the descriptors relevant in the assessment process, they were formulated starting from the learning objectives and the best possible learning outcomes, taking into account the particular subject in which these skills are taught [15].

For the purpose of this study, we refer to Q1, Q2 and Q6 in the ACTA assessment model, which are associated with critical thinking skills. Accordingly, we further develop this model, listing the specific descriptors in the form of analytic rubrics, so as to assess separate, individual parts of the student's performance and to sum the individual scores in order to obtain a total score [cf. 15-18].

2.2 Participants

The target group of our research consisted of 50 BA students from the University of Craiova, enrolled in FL programmes (Language and Literature) and trained to become FL teachers. The participants were chosen on a volunteer basis and the assessment activity took place in the classroom in the form of an FL practical course. The group was a rather homogeneous sample of students majoring in foreign languages, aged 20-23, with women outnumbering men with a three-to-one margin.

2.3 Data analysis

The answers were content analysed based on a set of specific descriptors associated to critical thinking assessment, specifically designed for this problem-based test. The answers were assessed matching the student's performance against this set of criteria as detailed in Tables 1-2. To measure the level to which a student meets the criteria for the tasks, we created a scoring scale, comprising analytic rubrics [cf. 16], scoring rubrics for each of the descriptors, and their corresponding levels of performance [cf. 16-18]. The analytic rubrics reflect the explicit performance expectations for each level and allow to focus on the required type of answer, irrespective of the students' creativity. This made the assessment procedure more consistent and objective, yet time-consuming for the teacher, since every student's work was examined a separate time for each of the specific task and scoring criteria – interpretation and action. The advantage was that we could obtain both individual scores and group scores, starting from the interpretation and action structures scoring scales detailed below (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1. Scoring criteria for assessing critical thinking skills - interpretation structures (I1-I4).

Level	Non-autonomous	Weak	Intermediate	Advanced
No. of points	1	2	3	4
I1	identifies the purpose to which the video was created, with the teacher's guidance;	identifies the topic of the video instead of its purpose	identifies the purpose to which the video was created	identifies the purpose to which the video was created, distinguishing between topic and purpose
I2	identifies Greta's general point of view on actions against climate change	identifies Greta's point of view on the children's involvement in protests for their future	identifies Greta's point of view on the children's involvement in protests for their future and her opinion that such protests are more important than attending formal education	identifies Greta's point of view on the children's involvement in protests for their future and her opinion that such protests are more important than attending formal education, as well as their implications
I3	identifies Greta Thunberg's and Boyan Slat's actions and chooses between them, only if helped by the teacher	identifies Greta Thunberg's and Boyan Slat's actions and chooses between them	identifies the complementarity of Greta Thunberg's and Boyan Slat's actions and chooses between them	identifies the complementarity of Greta Thunberg's and Boyan Slat's actions and chooses between them, pointing out their strengths and weaknesses
I4	identifies the role of media in conveying Greta Thunberg's messages, only if helped by the teacher;	identifies the role of media in conveying Greta Thunberg's messages and in transforming her into a climate icon	identifies and explains the role of media in conveying Greta Thunberg's messages and in transforming her into a climate icon, supporting the explanation with concrete data (number of YouTube views, Google hits)	identifies and explains the role of media in conveying Greta Thunberg's messages and in transforming her into a climate icon, supporting the explanation with concrete data (number of YouTube views, Google hits), distinguishing between traditional and new media

Based on the scoring grid in Table 1 above, the students were given 0, 1, 2, 3 or 4 points, depending on the degree to which their answers have met each criterion. For example, a student whose answer did not meet any criterion or who provided no answer, was given zero points for the respective descriptor. On the other hand, a student who provided answers that fully met the criteria for all descriptors was given a maximum of 16 points. Thus, the levels for interpretation structures were established based on the total number of points obtained, namely: level Non-autonomous for 0-4 points, level Weak for 5-8 points, level Intermediate corresponded to 9-12 points and level Advanced were considered the students with 13-16 points.

The same procedure was applied in the case of assessing the level of critical thinking regarding the action structures. In Table 2 below, we present the five specific descriptors and the scoring grid associated with them:

Table 2. Scoring criteria for assessing critical thinking skills - action structures (A1-A5).

Level	Non-autonomous	Weak	Intermediate	Advanced
No. of points	1	2	3	4
A1	is able to structure his/her discourse only if assisted by the teacher;	uses logical connectors, but fails to clearly organize his/her discourse;	uses proper logical connectors to express some of his/her own opinions;	uses proper logical connectors to express all his/her own opinions;
A2	expresses his/her own point of view without integrating additional information from other sources;	expresses his/her own point of view integrating additional information from other sources;	expresses his/her own point of view integrating relevant additional information from other sources;	expresses his/her own point of view integrating relevant additional information from other sources, approached from a critical and a comparative perspective;
A3	is able to motivate his/her answer, only if helped by the teacher;	is able to motivate his/her answer referring to his/her own educational system and his/her own experience without providing any concrete examples;	is able to support his/her answer with 1 concrete example from his/her own educational system and his/her own experience;	is able to support his/her answer with 2 concrete examples from his/her own educational system and his/her own experience;
A4	chooses between Greta's or Boyan's actions without motivating his/her answer;	chooses between Greta's or Boyan's actions and draws up a comparative analysis;	chooses between Greta's or Boyan's actions and draws up a comparative critical analysis;	chooses between Greta's or Boyan's actions and draws up an accurate and complete comparative critical analysis;
A5	formulates his/her viewpoint regarding the role of media in the fight against climate change, only if helped by the teacher.	clearly formulates his/her viewpoint regarding the role of media in the fight against climate change.	clearly formulates his/her viewpoint regarding the role of media in the fight against climate change, providing general examples.	clearly formulates his/her viewpoint regarding the role of media in the fight against climate change, providing concrete, real-life examples.

Again, the students were given 0, 1, 2, 3 or 4 points, depending on the degree to which they met each of the five descriptors associated to action structures. For example, no answer or an inappropriate answer was again marked with zero points, whereas a student with fully compliant answers against all five descriptors was given a maximum of 20 points. The levels were then established based on the total number of points that every student scored, namely: level Non-autonomous for 0-5 points, level Weak for 6-10 points, level Intermediate corresponded to 11-15 points and level Advanced for 16-20 points.

The use of scoring grids in analysing the students' answers to the three open-ended questions allowed us to perform an efficient, objective evaluation. Moreover, by using open-ended questions, the students were encouraged to formulate and justify their ideas, based on their own understanding, which allowed us to evaluate the students' reasoning and to better identify which critical thinking skills were the most used [19].

3 RESULTS

As explained in the previous section, the results were obtained based on classifying the students' level of critical thinking according to the total score awarded for their answers. This distribution on levels helped us distinguish between weak performance and good performance, or between non-autonomous and independent performance when evaluating the students' level of competence and to provide more detailed feedback when needed. Moreover, it enabled us to identify critical (low-scored) areas, as well as areas that need improvement, as far as both linguistic and transversal competences (i.e. critical thinking) were concerned.

In the first subsection, we present the results regarding the level of critical thinking of LF students for interpretation and action structures, and focus on the correlation between the two for the overall group. In the second subsection, we compare the score distribution for each descriptor defining the two structures, pointing to the advantages of using such tools in the assessment of transversal, as well as linguistic competences.

3.1 Levels of critical thinking skills

In determining the level of critical thinking of the sample group, we graded the students' answers, awarding a number of points in accordance with the scoring grid, and ranked them based on their corresponding level.

Figure 1 presents the percentages of students at each level of performance for the interpretation structure, which shows how the students comprehend and interpret the proposed problem-based test.

More specifically, 10% of the overall sample needed assistance from the teacher in solving the task or they just did not solve it at all, 14% qualified as weak, 30% as intermediate, whereas approximately half of the sampling group (46%) ranked at the advanced level.

Figure 1. Level of critical thinking – interpretation structures.

Regarding the action structures, Figure 2 shows the percentages of students at each level of performance, showcasing how the students act to solve the proposed problem-based test. Thus, more than half qualified as non-autonomous and weak, and only 16% reached the advanced level.

Figure 2. Level of critical thinking – action structures.

In order to see if there is a correlation between interpretation and action structures, we compared the group results for both criteria. As illustrated in Figure 3 below, there is evidence to claim that the two structures are not correlated, in the sense that there is a reversed distribution of levels: the highest percentage of students were listed as advanced for interpretation structures (46%), whereas, for the action structures, only 16% of the students reached an advanced level and 32% were evaluated as non-autonomous.

Figure 3. Comparison between interpretation and action structures.

The reversed level distribution strengthens the idea that the students were previously confronted with topics that challenged their critical thinking skills, but have not been actively engaged in solving them. In other words, the students proved to be aware of the issues raised in the test, with more than 70% scoring intermediate and advanced levels for the interpretation structures, but over half of them could hardly demonstrate the ability to adequately complete the tasks related to action structures. Surprisingly, the percentage for the non-autonomous level for action structures is quite high and it is an indicative of their lack of or disinterest in taking attitude or getting involved, and not of their lack of comprehension skills or language skills, since no student complained during the test that they did not understand the tasks.

Nonetheless, the group results reflect that the FL students have the potential to become actively engaged, especially if more emphasis is placed on developing transversal skills during their academic training or if opportunities arise for them to get more involved at personal or group level. In our opinion, this is a good indicator of their capacity to turn into mindchangers in their future career.

3.2 Score distribution for the interpretation and action structures

In order to identify the deficient areas in our FL students, we analysed the total group scores for each descriptor' analytic rubrics. By looking at the data provided in Figures 4 and 5 below, we see that the score distribution is again unbalanced between the specific descriptors corresponding to the interpretation structures (I1-I4) and action structures (A1-A5).

Overall, the results indicate that students are basically able to identify general topics, purposes, points of view, opinions, but fail to analyse, evaluate, explain, compare, find examples, and provide additional information in a coherent and cohesive argumentation. This enabled us to conclude that there is a stringent need for such particular assessment exercises that capture the specificities of these functions.

When drawing up the descriptors, we started from the idea that students should already be equipped with critical thinking skills before they enrol at university, since during their upper secondary studies, these competences are included in the curriculum and developed as specific competences at disciplines that are part of the Language and Communication curricular domain. Basically, such competences refer to the ability of the students to identify, understand, make connections between ideas and their own arguments, detect reasoning errors in arguments and presentations, solve complex problems, identify the context and implications of an argument/idea, identify and understand the justifications behind opinions/beliefs, build new arguments and ideas based on those already accumulated, or distinguish between facts/opinions/value judgements [20 p4-6]. Therefore, our expectation was that they would put such skills into practice and would be able to demonstrate them when confronted with issues related to environmental protection, even if they were not used to dealing with such topics during their FL classes at university. The overall results did not reflect the expectation, as demonstrated below.

In the problem-based test, the descriptors I1-I4 for the interpretation structures were meant to be correlated with the questions, namely I1 corresponded to Q1, I2 to Q2, I3 to Q6a and I4 to Q6b. As regards the descriptors for the action structures, A1-A3 were supposed to be checked in the answers to all the questions, whereas A4 was correlated with I3, and A5 with I4, which we consider to be the most complex descriptors for the interpretation structures.

Figure 4. Score distribution for interpretation structures.

Figure 5. Score distribution for action structures.

Indeed, the descriptors I3 and I4 are of particular interest, because they target the students' ability to stand for a particular point of view, to justify their choice with evidence, to identify strengths and weaknesses, to ground their opinions and build their arguments on additional information, previous experience or simply on in-class research activity by means of their immediate resources (i.e. mobile phones or other media devices). This is where our students scored the lowest number of points, with almost a quarter of the students being awarded 0 or 1 point, which is reflected in the overall score for I3 and I4 presented in Figure 4.

Even more unfortunate are the score results for the correlated descriptors of the action structures, A4 and A5, which are the lowest in the grid. If the students encounter difficulties in comparing between two given points of view (I3 and I4), they find it even more difficult to state their own point of view, to support it with a well-structured and valid argumentation, and to get involved in the world they live in with personal solutions to common issues.

To summarize, the results reflect the students' ability to develop and express independent opinions and to reflect about the world around them, but not their ability to participate in it. Our strong belief, supported by the results of this study, is that teachers, as well as students, should take the next step forward and make the shift from awareness to active engagement.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, this study indicated that, despite the fact that the national educational policies and the labour market acknowledge the importance of critical thinking skills and attest their inclusion and development in formal training, the level of such skills at the Romanian students is low. This confirms the need to identify solutions that could be put into practice to remedy the deficiencies and obtain valid results that can be subsequently measured, which is in line with the OECD recommendation that Romania's teachers need to be provided with more support to reliably assess student work, so that they could provide students with the feedback they need [8 p14].

Moreover, the approach used here, which was based on analytic scoring rubrics, proved advantageous for the improvement of the level of critical thinking in the particular case of FL students, for several reasons.

Firstly, this type of scoring, which Muller [16], Mertler [17] and Hafner&Hafner [22] claim to be a useful, efficient and reliable tool in educational practice in general, proved to be a good instrument for an objective and consistent evaluation of students' critical thinking skills. Furthermore, we consider that the content of the rubrics can be adapted to various disciplines when dealing with critical thinking. In our case, the scoring rubrics were particularly useful as it kept us focused on the relevant aspects during the assessment process, but could also help to identify the exact students' deficiencies, as well as possible means to overcome them. Such tests have the potential to promote learning and/or improve instruction, because when the teachers use rubrics, they make expectations and criteria explicit, which also facilitates feedback and self-assessment [22].

Secondly, for FL teacher trainers, the use of this analytic scoring rubric make it possible to establish the specific strengths and weaknesses [17] of individual students or of a group of students as regards the development of critical thinking skills in formal education, especially if a formative feedback is the goal.

In other words, it could help them adapt the course content so as to develop the relevant competences for the labour market, lifelong learning and active engagement. It could also improve the FL teachers' capacity to design activities for the development and assessment of critical thinking in language classes, emphasizing the role of language teaching/learning in building up a new generation of active and responsible citizens on the one hand, and bringing new perspectives in the existing curricula for teacher training study programmes, on the other hand.

Last but not least, for FL students, the use of such tools is beneficial, because it allows the teacher to bring new topics into the classroom, different from the more technical, subject-specific ones. In the case at hand, the feedback provided at the end of the test showed that the students appreciated the changes in the structure of an FL practical course and the mixture between the tasks involving expressing opinions, stating and supporting facts, and foreign language production. Therefore, this may be a motivating activity, in which FL courses could be used to foster critical thinking - one such example is presented in Resceanu [23] - and critical thinking developing strategies could be used to improve FL competence.

In conclusion, the assessment tool used in this study could be designed in such a way that educators or students at all levels from FL study programmes may use it in order to create strategies for both the development, and the assessment of critical thinking skills.

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